

An Approach to Introduce High-School Students to the P-vs-NP Question

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Abstract. In this poster, we are concerned with a way to introduce high school students to the P vs NP question. It is intended to be used in a one hour lecture of the high school credit system in the fall this year. Our approach is novel in that the question is explained from the perspective of imaginable worlds. While this may look abstract to high school students who do not have mathematical backgrounds, it certainly has an advantage in that students can have opportunities to stretch their imaginations to understand different kinds of worlds. Since our goal of giving a lecture about the P vs NP question is not to teach students technical details but to help them understand different perspectives on the hardness of computational problems, we believe that our approach will be sufficient enough to achieve the goal.

Keywords: P vs NP question · a possible world · logical consequence.

1 Introduction

In this poster, we describe an approach that can be used to introduce high school students to the P vs NP question. The approach is different from typical ways by which the question is introduced in that structural properties of different worlds in which the question is addressed are used. We believe that this approach will help high school students become interested in the question because it does not require mathematical backgrounds and it can possibly foster creative thinking.

2 A Proposed Approach

Many researchers believe that P and NP are not the same. A different way of interpreting this belief is that it looks unlikely that a world exists in which solving a problem and verifying the validity of a given solution are equally hard [1]. Now, this question can be explained from the perspective of different worlds as follows.

1. First, we start with a hypothetical world (World 1) in which the problem of deciding whether an arbitrary quantified boolean formula is true or not (TQBF problem) is solved by an oracle in one step [2].

- (a) To explain this world to students, it is necessary to point out that there are different kinds of resources from the perspective of algorithms. Examples include time, space, network bandwidth, randomness, and interaction. In addition, we can emphasize that we need to pay some cost in the form of any of these resources in order to compute something. In other words, computation is not free.
 - (b) In World 1, $P = NP$. This implies that all NP complete problems can be solvable efficiently. After consequences of the existence of an oracle for the quantified boolean formula problem are explained, we may raise the following question. Is this the world in which we live? Although the answer seems to be no, no definite answer is known yet and it may be possible to have an unconventional computer that serves as this oracle in the future.
2. Second, we introduce Algorithmica [3] to students. Like World 1, $P = NP$ in this world. However, it is unlikely that Algorithmica and World 1 are the same. The difference between these worlds lies in the existence of an oracle that solves TQBF in constant time or not. In other worlds, even though $P = NP$ in Algorithmica, we do not know whether such an oracle exists in this world. On the other hand, there are many structural similarities between World 1 and Algorithmica because all logical consequences of $P = NP$ are true in both worlds. For example, inductive learning becomes an easy problem in both worlds. In addition, the RSA algorithm is no longer safe in both worlds [3].
 3. Then, we can introduce a world in which P is not the same as NP . One such world is Heuristica [3] where hard instances of NP complete problems exist, but it is difficult to find such hard instances. At this stage, we can select several structural properties of the worlds mentioned and raise the question, "What are properties that look true in the world where we live?"

3 Conclusion and Future Directions

In this poster, we described an approach that can be used to introduce high school students to the P vs NP question. It is different from typical ways of introducing the question in that possible worlds in which the question is addressed are explained. We believe that our approach can serve as an eye opener for high school students because they never have had such a perspective on the hardness of computational problems. In other words, students may be adept at solving mathematical problems taught in school, or they may be aware of physical laws such as Newton's laws of motion which govern our world, but they do not know a possibility of combining a world and mathematical problems addressed in the world. Once students get interested in the subjects, we can possibly mention additional worlds such as Optiland, Obfustopia, and a quantum world [4, 5]. In addition, it will be interesting to point out that a world can be analyzed in terms of almost everywhere solvability [6].

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